

Synthesis of some New Fluorine containing 1*H*-Pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines

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PYRAZOLE is one of the most important heterocyclic compounds amongst all the five-membered heterocycles from the medicinal point of view. Pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine derivatives are well known for various biological activities like hypotensive¹, hypoglycemic², cytostatic³, psychotropic⁴ and as coronary vasodilators⁵. Alcoholic derivatives of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines and their salts are useful as tranquilisers and antiinflammatory agents⁶. Recently⁷, we have reported the synthesis of the fluorinated 1*H*-pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines by condensing 1,3-disubstituted-5-aminopyrazole with 1,3-diketones in glacial acetic acid. 1,3-Disubstituted-5-aminopyrazole has been prepared by the condensation of benzoylacetonitrile with arylhydrazines in absolute ethanol⁸. We now report condensation products of 1,3-diarylprop-2-en-1-one with 1,3-disubstituted-5-aminopyrazole in glacial acetic acid in presence of sulphuric acid yielding 1*H*-pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines. 1,3-Diarylprop-2-en-1-one derivatives were synthesised by the reaction of fluorinated acetophenone with benzaldehyde in presence of base⁹. There are two possibilities for orientation of 1,3-diarylprop-2-en-1-one in this reaction which may result in the formation of two isomers 3 and 4 (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Structure of 1*H*-pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines have been confirmed by ir, pmr, ¹⁹F nmr and mass spectral studies. Ir spectra of these derivatives showed characteristic bands in the regions 1620–1700 (C=N), 1400–1580 (=C–N) and 1100–

1310 cm⁻¹ due to (=C–F) Pmr spectra (TFA) showed characteristic resonance signals in the region δ 6.7–7.9 due to presence of aromatic protons and methyl protons signal at δ 2.0–3.0 in compounds 3c, f and i, respectively. In pmr spectra, disappearance of methine proton =CH signal at δ 6.2 and amino proton (NH₂) signal at δ 3.4 ppm of 1,3-disubstituted-5-aminopyrazole confirms the complete condensation of 1,3-diarylprop-2-en-1-one with aminopyrazole. Further, formation of these derivatives was confirmed by ¹⁹F nmr spectral studies. Presence of fluorophenyl groups was confirmed by the appearance of sharp signals at δ 30–45. On the basis of ir and pmr studies, it is not possible to decide whether 3 or 4 is formed. The structure of the actual product as 3 could be established only on the basis of mass spectral studies. Compound 3j ionises under electron impact to give a molecular ion cluster peaks *I*, *m/e* 589, 591, 593 in the ratio of 76.6 : 100 : 24.4 corresponding to *M*⁺ and *M*⁺² and *M*⁺ of isotopic peaks due to isotopic abundance of one chlorine and one bromine. Formation of two species at *m/e* 155 and 157 (in the ratio of 3 : 1) and 434 and 436 (in the ratio of 1 : 1) provides a strong evidence for the formation of isomeric compound 3 and not 4.

Compounds 3c, d, e f and h were screened for their CNS activity, and found to be non-toxic and possess mild CNS depressant activity. Compounds 3c, d and h exhibit antiinflammatory activity.

Experimental

1,3-Diarylprop-2-en-1-one: The compounds were synthesised by the reaction of fluorinated acetophenone with benzaldehyde in presence of base⁹. Compounds 2d and 2e have not been reported earlier: 2d, recrystallised from ethanol, (18 g, 64%), m.p. 92° (Found: C, 64.51; H, 3.10 C₁₅H₉ClF₂O requires: C, 64.63; H, 3.23%); ν_{max} 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=O); 2e, yield (20 g, 72%), m.p. 140° (Found: C, 69.84; H, 4.25. C₁₆H₁₂ClFO requires: C, 69.94; H, 4.37%); ν_{max} 1650 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

1*H*-Pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines: To a solution of 1,3-disubstituted-5-aminopyrazole (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (20 ml) concentrated sulphuric acid (4 drops) was added with stirring at 0–5°. After 1 h, 1,3-diarylprop-2-en-1-one (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (15 ml) was added with stirring at the same temperature. When the addition was complete, the solution was refluxed for 6–8 h on a sand-bath. Excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting compound was recrystallised from ethanol/methanol. All the compounds were synthesised in a similar manner. Details of amount taken of different reactants, analytical and physical data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 1*H*-PYRAZOLO[3,4-*b*]PYRIDINE DERIVATIVES (3)

Sl. no.	5-Amino-pyrazole (in g)	Prop-2-en-1-one (in g)	M p. °C	X	Y	R ¹	R ²	R ³	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
										C	H	N
3a	2.6	2.9	145	H	Cl	Cl	F	F	C ₃₀ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ F ₂ N ₃	68.14 (68.18)	3.18 (3.21)	7.89 (7.95)
b	2.5	2.4	190	F	H	H	F	F	C ₃₀ H ₁₆ F ₃ N ₃	75.40 (75.47)	3.68 (3.77)	8.76 (8.80)
c	2.5	2.5	210	F	H	ClH ₂	F	F	C ₃₁ H ₂₀ F ₃ N ₃	75.71 (75.76)	4.01 (4.07)	8.48 (8.55)
d	2.5	2.7	240	F	H	Cl	F	F	C ₃₀ H ₁₇ ClF ₂ N ₃	70.31 (70.38)	3.29 (3.32)	8.17 (8.21)
e	2.5	2.2	223	F	H	H	F	H	C ₃₀ H ₁₉ F ₂ N ₃	78.34 (78.40)	4.09 (4.13)	9.10 (9.15)
f	2.5	2.7	200	F	H	CH ₃	F	Cl	C ₃₁ H ₂₀ ClF ₂ N ₃	73.25 (73.30)	3.89 (3.94)	8.20 (8.27)
g	3.3	2.2	215	F	Br	H	F	H	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ BrF ₂ N ₃	66.86 (66.90)	3.29 (3.34)	7.71 (7.80)
h	3.3	2.4	220	F	Br	H	F	F	C ₃₀ H ₁₇ Br ₂ N ₃	64.69 (64.74)	3.01 (3.05)	7.47 (7.55)
i	3.3	2.5	175	F	Br	CH ₃	F	F	C ₃₁ H ₁₉ BrF ₂ N ₃	65.21 (65.26)	3.29 (3.33)	7.30 (7.36)
j	3.3	2.7	185	F	Br	Cl	F	F	C ₃₀ H ₁₆ BrClF ₂ N ₃	61.00 (61.01)	2.68 (2.71)	7.07 (7.11)

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1,3-Dioxolo[4,5-*g*]quinazolines

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KEEPING in view the physiological importance of 1,3-dioxolo[4,5-*g*]quinazolines, some authors have reported^{1,2} the synthesis of 6-methyl-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-*g*]quinazolin-8(*7H*)-one (2a). Here we report a one-step synthesis of the same compound by the direct condensation of methyl-6-aminopiperonylate (1)³ with acetonitrile in the presence of dry HCl. Furthermore, a phenyl group has also been introduced in this system at position-6 by treating 1 with benzonitrile.

In the second approach, a phenyl group has been introduced in this system at position-7 by treating 1 with triethylorthoformate followed by the cyclisation of the intermediate, methyl-6-[(ethoxymethylene)amino]piperonylate (3) with aniline.

In the third approach, 6-methylthio/ethylthio-7-phenyl-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-*g*]quinazolin-8(*7H*)-ones (2d-e) have been synthesised by the condensation of 1 with phenyl isothiocyanate followed by reaction with methyl iodide or with ethyl bromide in the